

Chronic Sheehan's Syndrome

Dawood Shehzad* and Abdul Mutaal

Department of Medicine, Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi, Pakistan

Citation: Shehzad D, Mutaal A. Chronic Sheehan's Syndrome. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2023;2(17):1-2.

Received Date: 17 November, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 20 November, 2023; **Published Date:** 23 November, 2023

***Corresponding author:** Dr. Dawood Shehzad, Department of Medicine, Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi, Pakistan

Copyright: © Shehzad D, et al., Open Access 2023. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour* (ICMCRJ) (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

CLINICAL IMAGE

Our patient, a female in her late 30's, presented to the emergency department with complaints of emesis and diarrhea for the past three days. Emesis was acute in onset, non-projectile, contained gastric contents and was exacerbated with food intake. Diarrhea was also acute in onset, low volume, foul smelling, no particular exacerbating or relieving factors, and was associated with urgency. On review of systems, she endorsed shortness of breath, cold intolerance, patchy hair loss, decreased libido, and light headedness over the past eight years. Eight years ago she had a full-term spontaneous vaginal delivery of her fourth child. Her child was delivered at home and she reported excessive vaginal bleeding due to delayed expulsion of the placenta. At that time she was taken to a local hospital where she reported being admitted for fifteen days. After delivery, she was amenorrheic two months after the delivery and could not conceive or breastfeed her child.

On physical exam at our emergency room, she was found to have a blood pressure of 100/70 mm Hg while sitting with orthostatic hypotension on standing. Heart rate was 78 beats per minute, respiratory rate was 12 breaths per minute, and saturation was 94% on room air. On physical exam, she was drowsy but otherwise appeared to be lying comfortably in bed. She was hypovolemic on exam and her skin was noted to be dry. Loss of the lateral third of the eyebrows was noted. 1+ Pedal edema was noted. Her cardiovascular, respiratory, gastrointestinal, and neurological examinations were otherwise unremarkable.

Based on these findings a differential diagnosis of moderate to severe dehydration, Sheehan's Syndrome, Addison's disease, Hypothyroidism, Polyglandular syndrome type 2 (Schmidt syndrome), and Celiac disease was considered.

Her initial bloodwork was remarkable for a Hemoglobin of 11g/dL, creatinine of 0.7mg/dL (increased from her baseline of 0.7mg/dL), ALT of 66 units/L, and an otherwise normal electrolyte panel. Iron studies revealed evidence of microcytic anemia. A celiac panel and vitamin panel were negative.

The thyroid function panel was remarkable for normal TSH and an FT4 of 7.97 ng/ml (normal range 52–127 ng/mL), prolactin of 14.1 uIU/mL (54-490 uIU/mL), LH of 1.60 IU/L (1.80–11.78 IU/L), IGF-1 14.7 nmol/L (normal 18.4-37.12 nmol/L), normal fasting C-peptide, normal morning ACTH, normal fasting insulin.

An MRI Brain with and without contrast was ordered which revealed an empty sella. (Figures 1 & 2). Her acute episode was treated and she was discharged on prednisolone 7.5mg per day with proton pump inhibitors, thyroxine 112 mcg per day and combined estrogen and progesterone therapy with follow up after 2 weeks. She reported significant improvement of symptoms at follow up.

Figure 1: Absent Sella appreciated in the sagittal T2 image.

Figure 2: Absent sella tucica in the coronal T1 section clearly appreciated.